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Research Article

**A RESEARCH STUDY ON THE GREAT STORM OF THE
COVID-19 HOW WE MANAGE THE HYPERGLYCEMIA IN
MAYO HOSPITAL LAHORE**¹Aroosa Khalid, ²Sara Ansari, ³Javeria Tariq
¹Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur**Article Received:** October 2020 **Accepted:** November 2020 **Published:** December 2020**Abstract:**

We performed this study in the Mayo hospital Lahore. It is observed that the patient have the type 2 diabetes and the corona virus at the same time the condition become very crucial this time. Covid 19 and the type 2 diabetes are the most spreading diseases in the world about 12 million people died due to the type 2 diabetes in the world. So you can take the result from this that how it takes the lives of human what is this disease and how it takes the lives of millions of the human. In type 2 diabetes patient have the higher level of sugar and the glucose level of the body very high. We observed this in previous studies that how the human level of sugar and the glucose level in the human we also observed that the we performed the different studies on the mices and also the hc subjects. It is observed that the how the type 2 diabetes exist in the insulin therapy we increases the production of beta cells so that the proper observance of insulin exist in the body and the patient starts healing. Now the covid 19 is usually called the corona virus its starts in the big city of china called Wuhan it is a disease that covers entire world. It is observed that this disease comes from the rats. This disease spread as a fire in the entire world. It is observed that the patient have the type 2 diabetes and the virus same the condition become very crucial in this case. It is observed that the how we implement the glucose and the insulin level at the same time. It is observed that the it is the great challenge for the mayo hospital Lahore. It is observed that the patient have the respiratory disease called the corona virus called covid and also have the disease called the type 2 diabetes in this the condition of the patient become crucial.

Keywords: Covid-19, type 2 diabetes, crucial condition, maintenance of the glucose and the hyperglycemia.**Corresponding author:****Aroosa Khalid**

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INTRODUCTION:

The disease called the corona virus is the most spreading disease in the world it is observed that the over the 4 million cases are confirmed this cases are only the confirmed cases but this disease is still growing. It is observed that the how the type 2 diabetes exist in the insulin therapy we increases the production of beta cells so that the proper observance of insulin exist in the body and the patient starts healing. Now the covid 19 is usually called the corona virus its starts in the big city of china called Wuhan it is a disease that covers entire world. It is observed that this disease comes from the rats. This disease spread as a fire in the entire world. It is observed that the corona virus effects the all type of humans still they have another disease or not they are male or female it effects all. But the people who have the strong human respiratory system and the strong type of the immune system are able to manage with that type of the disease. The result of the patient have the covid 19 and the patient have the hypertension

increases the chances of more of dangerous as the whole world fighting with the corona virus. It is observed that the there is a bio connection between the chronic inflammation and the hyperglycemia.

METHODOLOGY:

As we studied above the corona virus is the most important disease in the entire world. It is observed that this disease is spreading like a fire in the entire world. To find the how we maintain a hyperglycemia in the mayo hospital Lahore. This study is performed in the mayo hospital Lahore. We have the profile of the patient having the covid 19 and the other disease called the hypertension and other life taking diseases. Following figure will show that the we selected the patient as we want according to the null criteria that have suffering from the covid 19 and have the problem of the respiratory system called the corona virus. And the maintenance of the hyperglycemia in the following figure.

In this studied we had find that there is a some relation between the blood glucose level and the serum level of the insulin as shown in the above figure. It is observed that the patient have the diabetes having not the any complex relationships. In

the following figure it is shows that the how the insulin dosing and which type of insulin we uses and how much we uses the insulin and on what time we gave the insulin to the patient. It is observed in the following table as shown in the following table

Table 1—Initial subcutaneous insulin dosing guideline for critically ill COVID-19 patients admitted with high glucose

BG 200–250 mg/dL	START SLIDING SCALE REGULAR INSULIN (insulin moderate to high dose scale)	MONITORING	
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> START SLIDING SCALE REGULAR INSULIN (insulin moderate to high dose scale) ADD BASAL INSULIN GLARGINE for patients with the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> T1DM on home insulin (75–100% basal dose) or >24 hr gap T2DM on insulin (25–50% basal dose) or >24 hr gap NPH may be appropriate basal for patients on steroids 	Check every 6 h	
BG 250–350 mg/dL. START SCHEDULED SUBCUTANEOUS INSULIN	HIGH SENSITIVITY	MODERATE SENSITIVITY	LOW SENSITIVITY
	No known diabetes, known DM with renal failure (eGFR <30), insulin resistance, steroid use	Known DM, renal failure (eGFR 30–50), immunosuppressive disease	Known DM, renal failure (eGFR <30), immunosuppressive disease
SCALE	0.1 units/kg/day	0.15 units/kg/day	0.2 units/kg/day
BOLUS	Approximate start dose (units/kg every 6 h), use clinical judgement	0.1–0.2	0.2–0.3
SCALE	Regular insulin every 6 h	Regular insulin every 6 h	Regular insulin every 6 h
FOLLOW TRENDS IN INSULIN USE: PROCAETONIN, DOWN, UP, AND FLUCTUATE TO GUIDE ON UPWARD OR DOWNWARD TITRATION OF INSULIN DOSE			
NO 250 mg/dL. INSULIN INFUSION NOT INITIATED OR VARIABLE INFUSION RATES HARD TO TRANSITION			
Regular insulin	BG (mg/dL)	Insulin (units/kg)	MONITORING
1st dose	>250	0.1	Hourly 2 h
2nd dose	>250	0.1	Hourly 4 h
3rd dose	>250	0.1	Hourly 6 h
4th dose	>250	0.1	Hourly 8 h
5th dose	>250	0.1	Hourly 10 h
6th dose	>250	0.1	Hourly 12 h
NO 250 mg/dL. TRANSITIONING FROM INSULIN INFUSION WITHIN A FEW HOURS VERY QUICKLY WITH SUBCUTANEOUS REGULAR INSULIN			
Regular insulin	BG (mg/dL)	Insulin (units/kg)	MONITORING
1st dose	>250	0.1	Hourly 2 h
2nd dose	>250	0.1	Hourly 4 h
3rd dose	>250	0.1	Hourly 6 h
4th dose	>250	0.1	Hourly 8 h
5th dose	>250	0.1	Hourly 10 h
6th dose	>250	0.1	Hourly 12 h
NO 250 mg/dL. SHORT DURATION OF INSULIN INFUSION TILL DRIP RATE STABILIZES			

In the above figure it is shows that the how much we gave insulin to the patient suffering from the corona virus and also have the which type of insulin is given how much insulin is given how many liters its injected and on what time it is injected and how it is injected it shows all the time.

RESULTS:

In this the great panademic it is observed that how we saves the life of a patient suffering from the covid 19 and also the type 2 diabetes as early ewe know that the patient have the type 2 diabetes in which patient have the higher level of sugar and the glucose level it is also observed that the patient have the respiratory system disease called the corona virus it is observed that the we have a proper plan for the injection of the

insulin and also for the how it is injected and what work is to be done. It is observed that the we arrange a special insulation word for the patient have the diabetes and the corona virus both it is observed that the we have the proper information that what we is being conducted and injected in the patient which level of insulin is being injected. The following table will show that the proper guidance of the treatment according to the start sliding scale regular insulin injected also for the according to the bg levels also due to the type 2 diabetes patients it will show. We also observed according to the pta and the tf from this we observed that the how much times it takes to given the proper treatment to the patient have the type 2 diabetes and the covid 19 both.

Table 2

DETAILED TREATMENT GUIDANCE BG 200–250 mg/dL		
1.	NO PRIOR KNOWN DIABETES or KNOWN DIABETES ON <2 ORAL AGENTS	MONITORING Check BG every 6 h
	• Check HbA _{1c} if none available in last 3 months	
	a Start sliding scale regular insulin: moderate to high dose and escalate scale if BG >250 mg/dL	
	b Add scheduled regular insulin every 6 h if TF initiated (see above for regular insulin dosing based on eGFR and hourly TF rate) + scale	
c Add scheduled regular insulin if BG remains >250 mg/dL + scale even if no TF initiated		
2.	KNOWN DIABETES PRIOR TO ADMISSION	Check BG every 6 h
	• Check HbA _{1c} if none available in last 3 months	
	a T1DM NPO: add basal insulin glargine ASAP (to avoid DKA): use 70% of home dose if eGFR >50 and 50% if eGFR <50 + scale	
	b T1DM on insulin pump and has supplies: if feasible, continue basal insulin via pump (use increased temporary basal rate if needed); rare use in ICU so calculate total basal as in a	
	c T1DM + TF: continue basal insulin (to prevent DKA) and add scheduled regular insulin for TF every 6 h (guidance above based on eGFR and TF rate) + scale	
	d T2DM NPO: on regimen that included insulin prior to admission: start 25–50% basal dose + scale	
e T2DM on insulin PTA + TF: start 25–50% basal dose and regular insulin for TF coverage every 6 h; see above for dose calculations + scale		

DISCUSSION:

In this we will show that the how and what treatment is given to the patient have the type 2 diabetes and also have infected from the covid 19. It is observed that the how the type 2 diabetes exist in the insulin therapy we increases the production of beta cells so that the proper observance of insulin exist in the body and the patient starts healing. Now the covid 19 is usually called the corona virus its starts in the big city of china called Wuhan it is a disease that covers entire world. It is observed that this disease comes from the rats. This disease spread as a fire in the entire world. It is observed that the corona virus effects the all type of humans still they have another disease or not they are male or female it effects.

CONCLUSION:

In this studied we will find that how the insulin and the glucose level of the body in the covid 19 patient and also have the diabetes. It is also observed that the patient have the type 2 diabetes have the highest level of sugar and the glucose level. It is also observed that the how we manage the hyperglycemia in this study. It is observed that the controlling the glucose level of the body is the very difficult step. We studied above about the tables of how the insulin is injected how much insulin is injected and which type of insulin is injected in the body it is a very difficult step to treat these two diseases it is observed that the patient have the diabetes and the covid 19 both are in the crucial position and both don't have any chances of live but the mayo hospital lahore is manage to treat these two diseases and have the proper treatment. In this studied we had find that there is a some relation between the blood glucose level and the serum level of the insulin as shown in the above figure. It is observed that the patient have the diabetes having not the any complex relationships. In the following figure it is shows that the how the insulin dosing and which type of insulin we uses and how much we uses the insulin and on what time we gave the insulin to the patient. It is observed in the above table as shown in the above table.

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